

An Inequality on the α -Zagreb Indices of a Graph and its Applications

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The first α -Zagreb index, denoted $Z_1^\alpha(G)$, of G and the second α -Zagreb index, denoted $Z_2^\alpha(G)$, of G are defined respectively as $\sum_{v \in V} d_G^{2\alpha}(v)$ and $\sum_{uv \in E} d_G^\alpha(u)d_G^\alpha(v)$, where α is a real number. In this short note, we present an inequality involving $Z_1^\alpha(G)$, $Z_1^{\alpha/2}(G)$, and $Z_2^\alpha(G)$, where $\alpha > 0$. The applications of the inequality are also discussed.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [2]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use $\omega(G)$ to denote the cliques number of a graph G . The first Zagreb index, denoted $Z_1(G)$, of G and the second Zagreb index,

denoted $Z_2(G)$, of G were introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [4]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index and the second Zagreb index are defined as $\sum_{v \in V} d_G^2(v)$ and $\sum_{uv \in E} d_G(u)d_G(v)$, respectively. The first Zagreb index and the second Zagreb index of G have been extended. See [5], [7], and [6]. We adopt the definitions for the first α -Zagreb index, denoted $Z_1^\alpha(G)$, of G and the second α -Zagreb index, denoted $Z_2^\alpha(G)$, of G as follows.

$$Z_1^\alpha(G) := \sum_{v \in V} d_G^{2\alpha}(v), \quad Z_2^\alpha(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} d_G^\alpha(u)d_G^\alpha(v),$$

where α is a real number. In this short note, we present an inequality involving $Z_1^\alpha(G)$, $Z_1^{\alpha/2}(G)$, $Z_2^\alpha(G)$, and the clique number of a graph, where $\alpha > 0$. The main result is as follows.

Theorem 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices and $e > 0$ edges. Assume α is a real number such that $\alpha > 0$. Then

$$\omega(G)(4Z_2^\alpha(G) + Z_1^\alpha(G)) \leq (2\omega(G) - 1) \left(Z_1^{\alpha/2}(G) \right)^2.$$

2 A Lemma

The proofs of Theorem 1 mainly depend on the following result obtained by Bonze in [1]. See also [8]. We will use it as a lemma in our proofs of Theorem 1 in Section 3.

Lemma 1 Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph of order n with clique number $\omega(G)$ and adjacency matrix $A(G)$. Define $S_n := \{ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) : x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n = 1, x_i \text{ is real and } x_i \geq 0 \text{ for each } i \text{ with } 1 \leq i \leq n \}$. Then

$$1 - \frac{1}{2\omega(G)} = \max_{X \in S_n} \left(X A(G) X^T + \frac{1}{2} X X^T \right),$$

where X^T is the transpose of X .

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1 Let d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n be the degrees of vertices in graph G . Define

$$x_i := \frac{d_i^\alpha}{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i^\alpha},$$

for each i with $1 \leq i \leq n$. Let X be (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) . Then $X \in S_n$. Applying Lemma 1 with $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \frac{1}{2\omega(G)} &\geq \frac{2 \sum_{uv \in E} d^\alpha(u)d^\alpha(v)}{(\sum_{v \in V} d^\alpha(v))^2} + \frac{\sum_{v \in V} d^{2\alpha}(v)}{2(\sum_{v \in V} d^\alpha(v))^2} \\ &= \frac{4Z_2^\alpha(G) + Z_1^\alpha(G)}{2 \left(Z_1^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}(G) \right)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Solving the inequality, we have that

$$\omega(G)(4Z_2^\alpha(G) + Z_1^\alpha(G)) \leq (2\omega(G) - 1) \left(Z_1^{\alpha/2}(G) \right)^2.$$

This completes the proofs of Theorem 1.

4 Applications of the inequality

Notice that $\left(Z_1^{\alpha/2}(G) \right)^2 = 4e^2$ when $\alpha = 1$. Let $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices and $e > 0$ edges. Then

$$\omega(G)(4Z_2(G) + Z_1(G)) \leq 4(2\omega(G) - 1)e^2.$$

Corollary 1 shows that for each lower bound on $Z_1(G)$ we can obtain an upper bound of $Z_2(G)$ and for each lower bound on $Z_2(G)$ we can obtain an upper bound of $Z_1(G)$. We can use the lower bounds on $Z_1(G)$ and $Z_2(G)$ in [3] to obtain respectively upper bounds for $Z_2(G)$ and $Z_1(G)$. The details for finding the upper bounds for $Z_2(G)$ and $Z_1(G)$ through using Corollary 1 are skipped here.

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